

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IN THE FORMATION OF INDEPENDENT THINKING IN LITERATURE LESSONS

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***Abstract.** In the pre-independence pedagogy, efforts were made to facilitate the educational process, to ease the learning activities of students as much as possible. This was a method aimed at reducing the amount of work that the child had to do. But with the passage of time, negative sides began to appear in the main method of simplified education, which is demonstration. Difficulties related to the student's independent thinking were banished from education based on the principle of demonstrability. All knowledge presented to the child in this education should be experienced, easy to learn, convenient to show and ready to deliver to the student. Such a requirement, first of all, blocked the direct relationship between the person who is the executor of education in well-equipped schools with great external opportunities.*

***Keywords:** pre-independence pedagogy, stories, conversations, lectures, problem exercises, work assignments, educational games, educational discussions, encouragement.*

At every stage of the educational process, today's teachers are given stories, conversations, lectures, problem exercises, work assignments, educational games, educational discussions; methods such as encouragement in the educational process and reprimanding, problem-based teaching of educational material, problem-based conversation, research, inductive and deductive discussions, independent work with a book, use of modern machines in education, oral inquiry, written work, creativity, programmed learning, independent control work are more or less understandable. However, today's pedagogy requires the formation of not only a mature, knowledgeable specialist, but also a healthy spiritual person, a well-rounded personality. To do this, it is necessary to teach teachers how to educate a perfect person, to provide them with methodological manuals and pedagogical materials necessary for this purpose. When talking about the development of independent thought, which is the basis of the formation of a healthy spiritual person, it is necessary to awaken the student's thoughts in the direct process of literary education, to create the necessary conditions for his active participation in educational work, to increase the activity of the student as a whole to keep during the lesson, to direct the student's thinking towards a certain goal in solving moral and spiritual issues, to organize his mental activity correctly, to encourage the child to think independently, express a reaction, draw conclusions.

Literature analysis and methodology.

Imam al-Bukhari, Imam Tirmidhi, Ahmad Farghani, Abu Nasr Farabi, Mahmud Kashghari, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Ibn Sina, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Ahmed Yassavi, Alisher Nawai and other scholars are those who thought about the education of a spiritually perfect person. In their views, attention is paid to the issue of teaching young people to think independently. V. Okon, M. Makhmutov, V. Kudravsev, V. Maransman, N. Mochalova, A. Matushkin, I. Ilniskaya and other methodist scientists and practicing specialists conducted scientific research on teaching students

to think independently. In the researches of a number of scientists, such as Abdulla Avloni, Hamza, S. Dolimov, S. Ismatov, Q. Ahmedov, A. Zunnunov, Q. Yoldoshev, T. Boboyev, S. Matjonov, M. Mirgosimova, T. Niyozmetova, S. Yaminova, O. Musurmonova, S. Nishonova, M. Inomova, etc., there are opinions on accustoming students to independent thinking. There are views of scientists such as S. F. Zhuykov on the formation of independent thinking in the first grades, and E. L. Belkin – on self-control during thinking process.

Discussion and results.

It is intended to raise independent thinking and research to the level of internal need. In literature classes, the student's understanding of the task and the purpose of study begins with the announcement of the purpose of the lesson by the teacher. That is, every literature lesson aimed at teaching students to think independently should begin with announcing its purpose to the students.

In the classification of methods, special attention is paid to the fact that they take into account the possibilities of human thinking and are based on facts and experience, and not to forcefully instill ready-made knowledge into students with their help. A number of pedagogues and psychologists have emphasized that general didactic methods such as problem-based, conversational, heuristic, research, comparison, inductive, and deductive methods are effective. The deeper teacher's knowledge of educational ways and methods is, the wider the opportunity to use them for a specific goal, the easier, productive, useful and lively the organization of each lesson will be. The mastery level of the lesson, in addition to its visuality and organizational perfection, requires the activation of students' independent thinking and their ability to apply theoretical knowledge in practice. "Educational methods," wrote M. Makhmutov, "must include all the information collected in the psychology of thinking at a new stage of student's development, which will allow them to improve the management of the process of mastering knowledge and activities."

Among the methods that ensure students' independent thinking in literature classes, the method of problem-based education is of great importance. Below we will talk about conversation, heuristic, research, comparison, inductive, deductive types of logical methods used in teaching students to think independently and their characteristics. The interview method is the main method after problem-based education in ensuring student's independent thinking. There are many works devoted to conversation in methodology science. In particular, the role and importance of the interview method in ensuring the effectiveness of literary education is revealed in A. Tajiyev's manual "Conversation in Literature Classes".

The research work of S. Matjonov is dedicated to the organization of students' independent work, and this process is a factor in the development of creative thinking, encouraging students to verbal and written creative work in literature classes is important for their development. Independent activities and creative work require independent thinking. A student who does not have an independent opinion and his own point of view cannot create, cannot work independently.

The importance of a well-organized conversation in the lesson is that it satisfies the needs of the young reader to talk about what he has read, express his attitude to it, and share his thoughts. Everyone accepts a work of art in its own way, at its own level. The student participating in the conversation discusses his thoughts and formulates them in words. This ensures that the thought is directed to a specific goal. During the conversation, the student needs to express his opinion and convince his interlocutors of its correctness. Based on the requirements of the teacher or peers, the ability to find evidence from the text of the work, to give examples is formed, the child gets used to making excuses and raising objections. During the conversation, the reader can express his

views and opinions only when he clearly knows the facts in the work or about it, but often, in such situations, knowledge and evidence are lacking. The student should be able to analyze them independently, think, draw conclusions.

Since the educational system of our republic is tasked with applying digital technologies and using their capabilities to determine the necessary directions for the development of the educational process, it is necessary to use it effectively in literary education, as well. Activation in the direction of digitalization, especially in the analysis of artistic works, can have a significant impact on the education of young people if it is carried out in literature classes. Because today, the use of digital technologies in all spheres is actively supported, especially in education. The use of digital technologies is the need of the hour for teachers of all fields, especially in teaching literature, which is considered a means of knowledge. The main task of this subject is to develop the spiritual wealth and humanity of students and to ensure that they fully master our literary wealth. It is known that conversation is a necessary means of communication in society. The importance of literature as a means of knowing the world is continuously increasing. Literature is a means of rational, logical knowledge of existence, and only with its help in the process of knowledge can generalization, understanding be connected with discussion and conclusion. Literature and speech are inextricably linked with thinking. Therefore, mastering literature with the effective use of digital technologies serves to develop thinking, and with the development of thinking, the student's thinking ability also increases. No matter how difficult it is, if we don't start this job today, we may be late then. The quality of educational processes can be dramatically improved in a short period of time by widely introducing digital technologies and increasing efficiency. First of all, it is necessary to analyze how digital technologies will be introduced. Serious preparation for the formation of a scientifically based approach to the introduction of digital technologies is required, as well as the study, systematization and generalization of the existing practice. It is possible to improve the quality of the influence of the environment on the Internet system on the minds of young people and seriously analyze many works offered in the field of literature. At the same time, digital technologies have a great role in making the lesson interesting and creating a sense of pleasure in learning. Emotion encourages the reader to enter the problem. That is the difference between the feelings of entertainment and the feelings of learning.

In conclusion, it can be said that today's youth is very different from ten years ago, and old-fashioned education is completely out of date when the fast flow of information is rapidly entering our lives.

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